

CHIEF EXECUTIVE OFFICER (CEO) CHARACTERISTICS AND CORPORATE TAX PLANNING IN NIGERIA

Eke Robert PhD, FCA¹; Aikowieren Efe Blessing² and Aigbevboile Aideloje³

Department of Accounting and Finance School of Management and Social Sciences, Wellspring University Benin City, Edo State.

¹robbyeke19@yahoo.com; Robert.eke@wellspringuni.edu.ng (+2348034712733); ²aikowieren45@gmail.com (+2348183883490); ³aigbevboileaideloje@gmail.com (+2348030719150)

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Abstract: The study examined the impact of Chief Executive Officer (CEO) characteristics on corporate tax planning of listed financial service firms in Nigeria from 2018-2022. The specific objective was to ascertain the impact of CEO age on corporate tax planning of listed firms in Nigeria; examine the influence of CEO tenure on corporate tax planning of listed firms in Nigeria and to investigate the impact of CEO financial expertise on corporate tax planning of listed firms in Nigeria. The study employed the ex post factor research design and descriptive and inferential statistics were employed to summarize and draw inference on the population studied. The ordinary least square was used to estimate the model of the study. The result of the analysis revealed that CEO age and CEO financial expertise have positive impact on corporate tax planning of listed financial firms in Nigeria. The study also found that CEO tenure have negative impact on corporate tax planning of listed financial firms in Nigeria. The study recommended that firms in the financial sector should sustain the policy of employing CEOs that are above 50 years, because they have the experience in handling tax related issues.

Keywords: Tax Planning, CEO Age, CEO Tenure, CEO financial expertise, Financial firms.

INTRODUCTION

Every profit-oriented firm's objective is to continue making money and remaining a continuing concern in its business operations. These businesses will go to whatever length to reduce expenses and costs while increasing profits. As a result, taxes are a substantial operational burden for these businesses, affecting their bottom line and financial situation. This is one of the reasons why the highest echelons of these companies push tax-saving methods and even contemplate utilizing "aggressive tax strategies" to reduce their tax burden.

The terms tax planning, tax aggressiveness or tax avoidance means the same thing. Martinez, Ribeiro, and Funchal (2015), on the other hand, believe that tax aggressiveness is to blame for the emergence of terminology like tax management, tax planning, tax sheltering, and tax avoidance in accounting literature. These phrases are now often employed in the same sentence. It is only an effort to use legal measures to avoid paying a significant tax obligation (Lambe, Orbunde, & Akinpelu, 2021). According to Hairul, Ibrahim, and Siti (2014), tax

aggressiveness is the deliberate decrease of a company's exact corporation tax payments. Tax aggressiveness is defined as a purposeful attempt to reduce the amount of taxes that should be paid by looking for loopholes in tax legislation by Blouin, Jagolinzer, and Larcker (2015). Tax aggressiveness is considered a rewarding activity because it involves a transfer of government wealth to the shareholders of a company (Khurana & Moser, 2013). The task of compiling a list of shareholder value-generating initiatives falls to the upper levels of a corporation. One of these tactics is tax planning to lessen the organization's corporate tax burden. Hambrick (2007) sounded that personality the upper echelon of an organization affect the firms decisions and values. The chief executive officer (CEO) of an organization plays a significant role. As the organization's senior management, they are more likely to see to it that the organization's goals and objectives are met. The current worldwide health crisis brought on by the Coronavirus epidemic has put the CEO's responsibilities in a company to the test (Aifuwa, Musa, & Aifuwa, 2020; Aifuwa & Gideon, 2022). The CEO may only be indirectly involved in the tax function, yet they are crucial in determining how company taxes are applied (Dyreg, Hanlon, & Maydew 2010).

The decision-making process and success of the company are influenced by the personal characteristics and qualities of the CEOs, such as age, tenure, financial knowledge, nationality, and gender; overconfidence, optimism, or risk aversion (Capalbo, Frino, Lim, Mollica & Palumbo, 2018). This study critically looked at the impact CEO attributes on corporate tax planning in Nigeria. The variable of interest includes CEO age, tenure, financial expertise and gender.

The CEO's age often serves as a key factor in the success of an organization's strategy and policies. According to Hambrick and Mason (1984), the youthful managers efficiently contribute to the expansion of the company. They create a strategy that is more supportive of innovation and risk-taking, which affects the company's financial performance and growth trends. Older managers, meanwhile, are more conservative and prioritize job security. In keeping with this example, having an older CEO in a firm would not provide an effective tax planning strategy since they do not easily grasp the quick change in the tax environment and do not take advantage of new tax possibilities.

CEO tenure is claimed to have a direct influence on an organization's financial success as well as tax policy. According to Holmstrom (1982), CEOs work more early in their tenure to positively affect the market opinion of their abilities. According to Ali and Zhang (2015), CEOs have an impact on market perception. This is frequently accomplished through increased discretionary accruals and increased disinvestment through asset sales and ceased activities (Pan, Wang, & Weisbach 2016). According to Powers, Robinson, and Stomberg (2016), CEOs should work harder or manage earnings and minimize income tax obligation early in their tenure in order to demonstrate superior financial success in the organization. Early CEO performance has a long-lasting impact on market opinions of their abilities (Capalbo *et al*, 2018). This is because the CEOs want to send a positive signal of their ability early in their careers Ali and Zhang (2015) asserted that CEOs in their early tenure in a firm have higher discretionary accruals and lower discretionary expenses than later in their tenure at the firm.

In accordance with the research of Hambrick and Mason (1984), the managerial decisions made by CEOs are significantly influenced by their professional background and expertise. A CEO with financial experience is more likely to have the knowledge and skills to develop an effective tax planning strategy. Additionally, these CEOs' financial backgrounds are important for developing effective tax planning methods (Custodio & Metzger, 2014).

There is evidence, according to Hui and Matsunaga (2015), that CEOs with a background in finance have superior disclosure practices. Therefore, by enhancing the internal information environment of a company, CEOs with financial competence might affect tax policy.

The female gender in top management position in an organization has been argued to perform far better than her male counterpart (Saidu & Aifuwa, 2020). Francoeur *et al.* (2008) put forward that women in top management position in an organization often bring a fresh perspective on complex issues, which could help correct informational biases in strategy formulation and problem solving. Female board members are tend to be more risk averse. In the audit committee, Abbasi *et al* (2020) report that the presence of a female director has a favorable impact on earnings management by increasing negative discretionary accruals, thereby decreasing income. However, there are claims by researchers that female CEO possess the traits of being less overconfident (Chen, Leung, Son, & Goergen, 2019), more risk averse (Bertrand, 2011; Faccio, Marchica and Mura, 2016) and more hesitant to participate in organizational or occupational fraud (Hanousek, Shamshur and Tresl, 2019). Drawing inspiration form the above argument, this study contributed to the literature on the impact of CEO gender in tax planning.

The demand for money has increased as the Nigerian federal government attempts to implement its development and infrastructure program. Since the price of crude oil has fallen in recent years, the federal government (FG) has grown more stringent and aggressive about how assessments are made and how much money is collected from current sources (Dennis & Emmanuel, 2014). Taxes are one of the main non-oil sources of revenue for the government since they are predictable, consistent, and they are required by law. Corporate earnings taxes in Nigeria are often a significant source of outflow for businesses

The Nigerian tax authorities are working harder than ever to increase tax collection (KPMG, 2018). In the years that have followed, a number of tax cases, such as Company Income tax have sparked intense discussion, including Citibank v. FIRS, TSKJ Construcoes Internacional Sociadede Unipersonal LDA v. FIRS, and CNOOC & SAPETRO v. NNPC & FIRS (KPMG, 2018), among others. These legal battles between companies and the tax authorities have an effect on the company's reputation.

In both accounting study and the corporate sector, CEOs have frequently been referred to as icons (Benjamin & Dabor, 2019). A CEO's popularity is based on his capacity to bring a dead company back to life and inject it with vitality so that it can stand up again. Less research has been done in the literature on how CEO characteristics affect business tax planning. Few researchers (Duong & Pallasch, 2021; Bashiru, Ba'ba & Bukar, 2020; Ba'aba & Bashiru, 2019; James, 2019; Huang & Zhang, 2018; Aliani, 2014) have looked at this occurrence. All these researchers except Alinani (2014) investigated the nexus of one or two CEO attributes on corporate tax planning. For example, Bashiru, Ba'ba and Bukar (2020) examined the impact of Corporate Governance Attributes on Tax Planning of listed Nigerian Conglomerate Companies. They found negative and significant relationship between CEO tenure, firm size and tax planning. Ba'aba and Bashiru (2019) examined the impact of Corporate Governance Attributes on Tax planning of listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria and Malaysia. They found that a negative and significant relationship between CEO tenure and firm size and tax planning.

From the above empirical literature and to the best of the resahcer's knowledge, no study have been carried out in the context of Nigeria on the impact of CEO age, tenure, financial expertise and gender on corporate tax

planning. The study tends to examine the impact of these CEO attributes on corporate tax planning in Nigeria. This study investigated the listed financial service firms in Nigeria from 2018-2022.

The broad objective of this study is to examine the impact of CEO Attributes on corporate tax planning of listed firms in Nigeria. The specific objectives are to;

1. ascertain the impact of CEO age on corporate tax planning of listed firms in Nigeria;
2. examine the influence of CEO tenure on corporate tax planning of listed firms in Nigeria;
3. investigate the effect of CEO financial expertise on corporate tax planning of listed firms in Nigeria;

The research questions and objectives were derived from the above objectives.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Conceptual Review

Corporate Tax Planning

The concept of tax corporate tax planning have been defined by different researchers, however, this study will adopt the definition of (Lee, Dobiyaniski & Minton 2015). Lee, *et al* (2015) defined tax planning as the deliberate effort of a company, using legal means or strategies, to reduce its tax liability. It is of a truth that individual or companies don't want to pay their taxes or pay less tax as much as possible. Ogundajo and Onakoya (2016) therefore noted that tax planning or tax aggressiveness has become an integral part of financial planning and the decisions offers a tax manager and the company opportunity to mitigate the company's tax liability and improve on the financial performance of the firm. The major goal of tax planning is to avoid tax which increases the financial statement expenses with the sole aim of increasing cash flows (Ayers, Call & Schwab, 2018).

Tax planning is conscious effort on the part of the tax payer to eliminate or reduce or spread tax liability without going against the law, by using all available allowances, exemptions, policies, guidelines, incentives and relief. Oyeshile and Adegbe (2020) highlighted some of the incentives and reliefs as specified in CITA, PITA and other laws as the commencement rule, investment allowance, pioneer status, cessation rule, investment allowance, exemption on interest on loan to foreign company wanting to do business in Nigeria and the timing of asset acquisition, claims of capital allowance. However, often a times taxpayer or companies may go beyond this incentive and relief and employ illegal means (tax evasion or fraud) such as intentional distortion or concealment of facts and figures with the intention of avoiding the payment of or reducing the amount of tax, otherwise payable. Maiga (2015) sounded that this acts of omission or commission might include: failure to pay tax for example withholding tax; failure to submit returns; omission or misstatement of items from returns; claiming relief (in Personal Income Tax), for example, of children that do not exist; understating income; documenting fictitious transactions; overstating expenses; failure to answer queries.

Effective Tax Rate ETR is the widely used measure of tax planning. This is because ETR helps to estimate the effectiveness in companies' tax planning activities (Mills, Erickson, & Maydew, 1998; and Phillips, 2003). While ETR is measured generally as the proportion of tax liability to accounting income, several variants have been documented in the literature. These variants are discussed are: (a) Accounting ETR: This is known as generally accepted accounting principles (GAAP) ETR in the US context. It is the reported ETR as par the financial statements. It is calculated as the total tax expenses divided by the accounting income before tax. Thus, it reflects the aggregate proportion of the accounting income payable as tax. It, therefore, measures tax planning relative to

accounting earnings. This measure has been used by Chen, Chen, Cheng, and Shevlin, (2010), and Armstrong, Blouin and Larcker (2012).

CEO Characteristics

The CEO occupies the peak of the organizational hierarchy, and he is ordinarily responsible for championing the course of the business from visioning, acquisition of requisite personnel to formulating the policy and setting the strategy for the organization (Ilaboya & Obasi, 2018). The CEO is the highest-ranking executive of any business organization. The CEO is known by other titles such as President, Executive director, and Managing director. CEOs differ in their natural endowment in terms of both demographic and cognitive qualities (Gabaix & Landier, 2007 and Murphy & Zbojnik, 2004). Therefore, the attributes of the CEO play a great role in shaping the performance of a firm.

CEO Age

The age of the CEO is a factor to consider in carrying out successful tax planning in firms. In literature there is a prominent argument that CEO age has an impact in corporate tax planning. For example, Gibbons and Murphy (1992), Holmstrom (1999); Prendergast and Stole (1996) argued that younger CEOs have greater incentives to favorably influence the labor market perception of their quality in order to obtain higher compensation and job security. Therefore, younger CEOs are more likely to adopt risky investment and financial policies (Crocchi, Giudice, & Jankensgard, 2017; Li, Low, & Makhija, 2017; Serfling, 2014). Contrariwise, older executives enjoy their “quite life” and prefer less risky investments (Bertrand & Schoar, 2003).

CEO Tenure

CEO tenure is another attribute that has been considered a factor that affects the corporate tax planning. Peni (2014) argued that CEOs with longer tenure make more meaningful contributions to firm value than short-tenured CEOs, thus employing tax planning strategies to achieve this feat. In contrast, Nguyen (2017); Serra, Tres, and Ferreira (2016); Tsai, Hung, Kuo, and Kuo (2006) contended that a longer CEO tenure does not contribute to firm value, thus they do not have tendencies to be tax aggressive.

CEO Financial Expertise

The financial expertise of the CEO is another factor to consider for successful corporate tax planning. Custodio and Metzger (2014) asserted that CEOs with financial background are have the technical know-how to pilot the affairs of the firm in issue of tax. They have tax avoidance skill help the firm reduce their corporate tax liability. Gallemore and Labro (2015) echoed that apart from the financial background of the CEO, the quality of their internal information environment also aids the successful tax planning strategies. Hui and Matsunaga (2015) provided evidence that CEOs with financial expertise result in better disclosure practice. Therefore, the CEOs with financial expertise could influence tax policy by improving a firm’s internal information environment. Custodio and Metzger (2014) added that CEO with financial expertise have the ability interpret the capital markets and reduce information asymmetry.

2.2 Theoretical Review

This study was anchored on Upper Echelon Theory. The Upper Echelon theory is used to provide theoretical understanding of the impact of CEO attributes on corporate tax planning in Nigeria. The Upper Echelon theory was postulated by Hambrick and Mason (1984) and it explains how managerial background attributes can reflect

tactical decisions. This study would critically examine how CEO attributes affect corporate tax planning in Nigeria. The upper echelons theory stresses the importance of the manager's role within the firm. According to this theory, the CEO can influence the value creation of firms through his style of management and personal skills. The CEO have the ability to employ corporate tax planning strategies to create value for the firm.

2.3. Empirical Review

Ilaboya and Aromwan (2023) examined the impact CEO attributes on and tax avoidance in Nigeria based on the framework of the upper echelon theory on managerial effects. The quantitative research design was employed in this study and data was gathered from the financial statements of sixty-six (66) non-financial firms listed on the NGX for 10 years (2009–2018). The model for the study was estimated using the generalised method of moments regression technique that helps address the issue of endogeneity. The results showed that the gender of the CEO, as well as the years spent, are significantly associated with tax avoidance within the Nigerian business environment. Consequently, the study concludes that the attributes of the CEO influence tax avoidance practices. In Spain, García-Meca *et al* (2021) examined the effect of chief executive officers' (CEOs) narcissistic tendencies on corporate tax avoidance. They further examined the moderating effect of two audit committee characteristics, size and gender, on the relationship between narcissism and tax avoidance. The study employed data set of 1303 firm-year observations from the period 2008–2017. The researchers found that CEO narcissism is positively related to tax avoidance. Narcissism is considered a personality trait that causes CEOs to implement tax avoidance strategies. However, this discretionary behavior is constrained by some audit committee characteristics. They further found that firms with larger audit committees help to control the consequences of CEO narcissism on tax avoidance. In addition, gender diverse audit committees are more sensitive to firm tax aggressiveness, and they reduce aggressive tax practices promoted by narcissistic CEOs.

Duong and Pallasch (2021) examined the effect of female CEO on tax aggressiveness in U firms. The study employed data from dataset of FTSE350 UK public companies between 2007 and 2015. The panel research design was employed for the study. They found that female CEOs are highly unlikely to be associated with tax aggressiveness and tax avoidance. These results are likely of interest to policy makers who are concerned about the implications of increasing the presence of female executives in the boardroom of public companies.

Bashiru, Ba'ba and Bukar (2020) examined the impact of Corporate Governance Attributes on Tax Planning of listed Nigerian Conglomerate Companies. The study adopts ex-post facto research design and utilized panel data from annual reports and accounts of the listed companies for the period of five years (2014-2018). The Data were analyzed using a panel regression technique to assess the effect of the independent variables on the dependent variable. The researchers' found a negative and significant relationship between CEO tenure, firm size and tax planning. They also found a positive relationship between BSIZE and ETR.

Ba'aba and Bashiru (2019) examined the impact of Corporate Governance Attributes on Tax planning of listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria and Malaysia. The corporate governance parameters include board size and CEO tenure while tax planning is proxied by the effective tax rate and firm size as control variable. The study adopts comparative and ex-post facto research design and will utilize panel data from annual reports and accounts of the listed companies for the period of five years (2014-2018). The Data were analysed using a panel regression technique to assess the effect of the independent variables on the dependent variable. The researchers found that

from random effect estimation model indicates a negative and significant relationship between CEO tenure and firm size and tax planning and a positive relationship between board size and tax planning.

James (2019) examined the impact of CEO age on tax planning in the United States of America. The researcher used got the data from Execucomp and a sample of 11,537 firm-year observations from the fiscal year 1997–2013. The panel least squares was used to test the hypotheses of the study. The researcher found that CEO age exerts an economically significant influence on firms' tax policies, incremental to economic determinants identified in prior research. Specifically, CEO age is positively related to cash and GAAP effective tax rates, and negatively related to permanent book-tax difference, suggesting that older CEOs are less likely to take actions to lower tax burden. The results hold across different model specifications and robustness tests to address potential bias arising from endogeneity, sample selection issue, and the confounding effect of CEO tenure.

Huang and Zhang (2018) examined the impact of financial expert CEOs on corporate tax avoidance. The researchers investigated the relationship between financial expert CEOs and tax avoidance both at the conditional mean and across tax avoidance distribution. The study employed data from standard and Poor (S&P) 1500 firms from the year 1993 to 2013 and excludes firms in the financial industry. Panel research design was adopted in the study and the panel least squares was employed to test the hypotheses of the study. The researchers found that financial expert CEOs are associated with a more aggressive tax avoidance policy.

Goldman, *et al.*, (2017) examined the effect of CEO tenure on corporate income tax planning and financial reporting decisions. The study employed the expos facto research design and data was gotten from Execucomp database. The panel research design was employed to test the hypotheses of the study. The researchers found that firms report lower GAAP and cash effective tax rates (ETR) early in the CEO's tenure, yielding both higher cash flows and after-tax earnings. They also found that firms have lower GAAP ETRs, but not cash ETRs, in the final year of the CEO's tenure, consistent with CEOs investing less in tax planning later in their tenure and instead using the tax expense to "window dress" earnings.

In the US, Francis, Hasan, Sun and Wu (2016) examined the impact CEO political preference on corporate tax sheltering. The political preference was proxied as politically partisan CEOs and nonpartisan CEOs. The regression technique was employed as the inferential statistics of the study. The reaches found that political partisan CEOs are associated with a higher level of corporate tax sheltering than firms led by nonpartisan CEOs. They also found that republican CEOs are associated with more corporate tax sheltering even when their wealth is not tied with that of shareholders and when corporate governance is weak, suggesting that their tax sheltering decisions could be driven by idiosyncratic factors such as their political ideology. They further found that Democratic CEOs are associated with more corporate tax sheltering only when their stock-based incentives are high, suggesting that their tax sheltering decisions are more likely to be driven by economic incentives.

Aliani (2014) examined the effect of CEO characteristics on tax planning in US firms during the period 1996–2009. The study was hinged on the by the upper echelon theory to develop a new tax context and hypothesis. The CEO characteristics include age, educational level, expertise, tenure, seniority and experience. The generalized least squares was employed to test the hypotheses of the study. The researcher found that the educational level and specialty of the CEO significantly influence the tax strategy used by the firm. However, it was also found that experience, seniority, age donot have significant effect on tax planning in US firms.

From the above empirical studies carried, it was observed that CEO age, CEO tenure CEO financial expertise and CEO gender have not been investigated in Nigeria. Therefore, this study will examine the impact of CEO age, tenure, financial expertise and gender on corporate tax planning of listed firms in Nigeria. It is worth-knowing that these mix of variables have not been investigated in the Nigeria context.

3. METHODOLOGY

This study adopted the ex-post facto research design. The ex-post facto seeks to discover the factors associated with specific occurrences, outcomes, conditions, or types of behavior by analyzing previous events or already existing conditions in order to predict future outcomes. The justification for the adoption of the ex-post facto research design is due to the fact that in an ex-post facto research design events has already occurred (that is, scientific data is already available), hence, preventing the researcher from manipulating the data and outcome of the study.

The study covered 23 listed financial firms in the Nigerian Exchange Group (NGX) as 2022. This covers listed firms in Deposit money bank, Insurance, Mortgage Institutions, Microfinance banks, among others. The data used secondary in nature and carefully sourced from the financial statements/annual reports of selected listed firms in the financial sector of Nigeria. The data spans five years, from 2018 to 2023. The data was based on annual data as stated in the financial statements/annual reports of selected listed firms in the financial sector of Nigeria.

Method of Data Analysis

Descriptive and inferential statistics was used to analyze the data of the study. The descriptive statistics include the mean, minimum, maximum and standard deviation. The ordinary least squares regression was employed as the inferential statistic to test the hypotheses stated in the study. Diagnostics tests such as; serial correlation (Breusch-Godfrey Serial Correlation LM Test), normality (Histogram normality test), linearity (bivariate analysis –Pearson Product Moment correlation), constant residual error test (Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey Heteroskedasticity test) and multicollinearity (variance inflation factor test). The Hausman Test was done to know whether to estimate our model using either the random effect panel regression or fixed effect panel regression (Studenmund, 2014).

Measurement of Variables

Table 1: Measurement of variables

Variable	Proxy	Measurement	Supporting Scholars
Corporate Tax Planning (Dependent)	ETR	Tax paid divided by profit before tax. The Statutory Tax Rate is the official corporate tax rate; which presently in Nigeria is 30% of assessable profit.	Ali and Zhang (2015); Egbunike, Gunardi, Ugochukwu & Hermawan (2021)
CEO Attributes (independent)	CEO Age (CEOA)	the natural logarithm of the age of CEOs	James (2019); Serfling (2014)

CEO Tenure (CEOT)	The natural logarithm of the number of years a CEO has served as CEO	Baaba & Bashiru (2019); James (2019)
CEO Financial Expertise (CEOFE)	The natural logarithm of the number of CEOs that have financial expertise within the period considered.	Aliani (2014)

Source: Author’s Compilation, 2024

Model Specification

This study adapted the model of Aliani (2014) used in their study in examining the impact of CEO characteristics on corporate tax planning in US companies. The model was stated as;

In econometric form;

$$ETR_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 CEOA_{it} + \beta_2 CEOT_{it} + \beta_3 CEOFE_{it} + \epsilon_{it} \dots\dots\dots(i)$$

Where;

ETR = Effective Tax Rate;

CEOA = CEO Age;

CEOT = CEO Tenure;

CEOFE = CEO Financial Expertise

E = Error term

i—Cross Section

t ----Time series

Apriori = $\beta_1, \beta_4 > 0$; $\beta_2, \beta_3 < 0$

Data Presentation, Interpretation And Discussion

Descriptive Statistics

Table 2

Descriptive Statistics

Variables	Mean	Minimum	Maximum	Std. Dev	Observation
ETR	1.64893	0.00128	28.3833	5.54324	220
CEOA	54.04854	57.98332	72.03343	13.45432	220
CEOT	4.04443	2.34332	6.33432	2.4533	220
CEOFE	0.67293	0.0000	1.0000	0.22414	220

Source: Author’s computation, 2024

Table 2 shows the descriptive statistics of the data used in the study. The dependent variable – ETR had mean of 1.64893, with a minimum value of 0.00128 and a maximum value of 28.3833. Also, the standard deviation 5.54324, exhibited a considerable clustering around the mean. The independent variables – CEOA, CEOT and

CEOFE had means of 54.04854, 4.04443 and 0.67293, respectively. Also, the standard deviation of the independent variables exhibited a considerable clustering around the mean .

Table 3: Correlation Matrix

Variable	ETR	CEOA	CEOT	CEOFE
ETR	1.000			
CEOA	0.2344	1.000		
CEOT	0.4776	0.3110	1.000	
CEOFE	0.3491	-0.1244	0.1087	1.000

Source: Author’s computation, 2024

The linearity of variables (correlation matrix) as presented in Table 3 show that the variables exhibited both positive and negative relationship. This is seen in the association between CEOA and ETR (0.2344), CEOFE and CEOA (-0.1244). The strength of association between variable were below the threshold of 0.80, suggesting the absence of the problem of multicollinearity in the predictor variables (Studenmund, 2014). However, to further validate the veracity of this result, we employed the Variance Inflation Factor test.

Specification and Diagnostic Tests

We carried out various specification and diagnostics test in order to fulfill the basic assumptions of regression and they passed the tests. These include; Multicollinearity test, serial correlation test, constant residual error test, misspecification test and normality test.

Multivariate Analyses and Hypotheses Testing

Having fulfilled the five-basic assumption of regression; the ordinary least squares estimation technique was employed to test the hypotheses stated in the study. Hypotheses of the study were tested at 5% level of significance (that is, if p-value < 0.05 reject **H₀**, else do otherwise).

Table 4: Inferential Statistics – Ordinary Least Squares

Dependent Variable: ETR

Method: Least Squares

Date: 07/17/24 Time: 10:14

Sample: 1 220

Included observations: 220

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	-0.783898	0.388235	-2.019131	0.0466
CEOA	0.795719	0.265809	2.993572	0.0036
CEOT	-0.205594	0.094747	-2.169927	0.0328
CEOFE	1.358118	0.330087	4.114423	0.0131
R-squared	0.855922	Mean dependent var	0.436170	
Adjusted R-squared	0.732602	S.D. dependent var	0.498568	

S.E. of regression	0.380341	Akaike info criterion	0.985770
Sum squared resid	12.44071	Schwarz criterion	1.202220
Log likelihood	-38.33117	Hannan-Quinn criter.	1.073200
F-statistic	30.54329	Durbin-Watson stat	0.823531
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000		

Source: Authors' Computation, 2024

Table 4 above revealed the results of the ordinary least squares regression for the model of the study. The explanatory variables employed in the study significantly explain effects of CEO characteristics on corporate tax planning in Nigeria, F-statistics = 30.54329, $p < 0.05$. The adjusted R-Squared stood at 0.7326; that is about 73.3% of the systematic variation in the dependent variable (corporate tax planning) is caused by the explanatory variable used in the study. While about 26.7% of the variations are caused by other variables not included in the model but were adequately captured by the standard error of the regression, $SE = 0.380341$.

Test of Hypotheses of the study

We tested our hypotheses at 5% level of significance (that is, if p-value < 0.05 reject H_0 , else do otherwise).

H_{01} : There is no significant impact of CEO age on corporate tax planning of listed firms in Nigeria.

From the result in tables 4 above, it was found that There is positive and significant relationship between CEO age and corporate tax planning of listed firms in Nigeria, $\beta_1 = 0.795719$; $SE = 0.265809$, $p = 0.0036 < 0.05$. Therefore, this failed to accept the null hypothesis stated on the study, that there is no significant relationship between CEO age and corporate tax planning of listed firms in Nigeria.

H_{02} CEO Tenure has no significant impact on corporate tax planning of listed firms in Nigeria

Result from the regression revealed that CEO tenure has negative and significant influence on corporate tax planning of listed firms in Nigeria, $\beta_2 = -0.205594$; $SE = 0.094747$, $p = 0.0328 < 0.05$. Therefore, the study failed to accept the null hypotheses that CEO tenure has no significant influence on corporate tax planning of listed firms in Nigeria.

H_{03} CEO financial expertise has no significant effect on corporate tax planning of listed firms in Nigeria

From the result in table above, it was revealed that CEO financial expertise has no significant effect on corporate tax planning of listed firms in Nigeria, $\beta_3 = 1.358118$; $SE = 0.330087$, $p = 0.0131 < 0.05$. This result simply implies that an increase in CEO financial expertise will significantly increase the corporate tax planning of listed firms in Nigeria.

Discussion of Findings

The study investigates the effects of CEO characteristics on corporate tax planning in listed financial firms in Nigeria from 2018-2023. First, it was found that CEO age has positive and significant impact corporate tax planning of listed financial firms in Nigeria. The result of this study is not consistent with works of James (2019) who also positive association between CEO age and corporate tax planning in listed financial firms in Nigeria. However, Aliani (2014) found no relationship between CEO age and tax planning of listed financial firms in Nigeria.

Secondly, the study found that CEO tenure has negative and significant effect on corporate tax planning of listed financial firms in Nigeria. The findings of this study consistent with works of Bashiru, Ba'ba and Bukar (2020); Goldman, *et al.*, (2017) who also found negative association between CEO tenure and corporate tax planning. However, the finding of this study is in dissonance with the work of Aliani (2014) who found no relationship. Thirdly, the study found that CEO financial expertise have positive and significant impact on corporate tax planning of listed financial firms in Nigeria. This result is consistent with works of Huang and Zhang (2018); Aliani (2014) who also found positive association between CEO financial expertise and corporate tax planning

Summary of Findings

The study investigated the effects of CEO characteristics on corporate tax planning of listed financial firms in Nigeria from 2018-2022; with its findings summarized thus:

- i) CEO age has positive and significant effect on corporate tax planning of listed financial firms in Nigeria;
- ii) There is negative and significant impact of CEO tenure on corporate tax planning of listed financial firms in Nigeria;
- iii) CEO financial expertise have positive and significant impact on corporate tax planning of listed financial firms in Nigeria; and

Conclusion

This research work investigated the effects of CEO characteristics on corporate tax planning of listed financial firms in Nigeria. The study concluded that CEO age and CEO financial expertise positively affect corporate tax planning of listed financial firms in Nigeria; while CEO tenure have negative impact on corporate tax planning of listed financial firms in Nigeria.

Recommendations

Based on the finding of this study we recommended the following;

1. Firms in the financial sector should sustain the policy of employing CEOs that are above 50 years, because they have the experience in handling tax related issues;
2. Statutory authorities in the financial sector should review the policy of the CEO tenure so as to reduce the tax liability of the firms;
3. CEOs with financial expertise should be employed in the firms so as to reduce the tax liability of the firms; and

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